

PHASE BEHAVIOUR OF SODIUM OLEATE IN NUJOL

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The changes in the phases of sodium oleate in different proportions of Nujol at various temperatures have been studied. It is found that the systems show the existence of the following phases: (i) isotropic liquid, (ii) neat soap, (iii) middle soap, (iv) waxy soap, (v) soap curd and (vi) fine soap particles behaving unlike soap crystallites.

The determination of the phase behaviour of soaps in hydrocarbon solvents is of importance in the study of the application of these systems as high-temperature greases. Also the attendant determination of the solubility of the soap in the solvent may prove useful for understanding the phenomenon of gelation occurring in such systems with certain concentrations of the soap. The previous work in this direction includes the study of (a) sodium palmitate in some organic solvents (Vold, Legget and McBain, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, **44**, 1058; 1942, **46**, 429), (b) sodium and calcium stearates in cetane (Vold *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, **50**, 39; *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 1424; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 2006), (c) lithium stearate and lithium 12-hydroxystearate in some hydrocarbon oils (Evans *et al.*, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1952, **2**, 252), (d) sodium phenylstearate in benzene (Honig and Singleterry, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 201), and (e) aryl stearate in benzene (Honig *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, **60**, 1114). The present investigation deals with the study of the behaviour of sodium oleate in Nujol using the visual method (McBain *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1970).

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials used were sodium oleate manufactured by B.D.H. (containing excess acid = 0.001 equivalent per mol. for the acid recovered from the soap; eq. wt. = 284.5 and I.V. = 88.34.) and Nujol, a product of Messrs Stanco Incorporated, New Jersey, U.S.A. ($d = 0.8753$; $\mu = 1.4810$ at 30°). The soap was dried to a constant weight at 105° . Requisite amounts of soap and Nujol (total weight about 0.5 g.) were weighed out into a small pyrex glass test tube of length 3" and diameter 0.4", with a constriction at a distance of about 1.5" from the bottom. The tube was then evacuated until air bubbles had ceased to evolve from the system. It was then sealed under vacuum by heating at the constriction. The tubes were then heated in an air-oven made of asbestos cement sheets in the form of a cube of 8" side. This was heated by two heating coils. The oven had a rotatable iron shaft, running across its length, which carried a circular iron disc (diameter 5.5") in which were cut six radial slits of 1.5" $\times$ 0.5". Each slit had two breadth-wise projections, one of which, situated near the centre of the disc, had a hole in it whereas the other served as a groove in which a screw with a concave bottom could be moved. A filled tube could be held in position by inserting its sealed end in the hole in one of the projections and by bringing the concave bottom of the screw in the other projection to press

against the bottom of the tube. The two heating coils were connected in parallel with each other and in series with a variable resistance, an ammeter and a 230 volt D.C. output.

This arrangement allowed six samples to be heated simultaneously. Any one of them could be brought at will against the windows provided in the walls other than those which carried the shaft. These windows were covered with optical glass for observation. The sample could be shaken vigorously, whenever required, by rotating the shaft rapidly. This was necessary to get a macroscopically homogeneous sample for examination. No serious temperature gradients were observed since calibrated thermometers maintained at different levels in the oven, showed the same reading. A 100 c.p. point-o-lite was used as a source of light.

Procedure.—The systems were heated until they completely melted into a homogeneous isotropic liquid and were then cooled to various low temperatures being allowed to remain at each temperature for 3 hours. Visible changes that could be observed with or without the help of nicols were recorded. Particularly, the following changes were observed with a fair accuracy employing, when necessary, slow heating over a narrow range: (i) the temperature, T_i , at which an anisotropic material first appeared in the system; (ii) the temperature, T_g , at which the system thickened to a consistency high enough to prevent it from flowing when the tube was inverted; (iii) the temperature, T_c , at which the system first started forming soap curd. The appearance of the tubes was also observed at various intervals on standing at room temperature and was found to remain essentially unchanged.

The values of T_i , T_g , and T_c in degrees centigrade, determined for various compositions are recorded in Table I in which the compositions (c) are expressed in terms of the weight of soap in 100 g. of the system. The appearance of the systems on cooling is briefly described in the last column of Table I.

TABLE I

Transition temperature of sodium oleate-nujol system.

	c .	T_i .	T_g .	T_c .	Changes in appearance.
A	100.00	247°	237°	196°	Homogeneous isotropic liquid (=H.i.l.) gave neat soap which changed to waxy soap and then curd.
B	84.95	228°	216°	190°	
C	76.25	221°	207°	188°	
D	61.27	219°	206°	186°	
E	49.98	217°	178°	196°	H.i.l. gave neat soap & then separated into layers: isotropic liquid at the top and middle soap below; the upper layer became anisotropic and the layers then diffused and soap curd was developed all over the system.
F	39.30	206°	170°	175°	
G	25.32	176°	166°	166°	H.i.l. became viscous and formed a deposit of crystallites; the liquid then became anisotropic and the mass gave a loose gel which developed soap curd.
H	19.96	174°	167°	...	Similar to that in G except that no curd was formed. Same as above except that the gel formed was more rigid.
I	9.37	174°	172°	...	
J	5.09	166°	188°	}	H.i.l. became viscous, set to a clear transparent gel which developed a slight opacity on cooling.
K	2.92	155°	186°		
L	0.98	125°	170°		

DISCUSSION

Though the method used allows transition temperatures to be determined only within a certain limit of accuracy, these observations suffice to provide a qualitative picture of the phenomena which occur on cooling the soap-solvent systems.

Curves I to III (Fig. 1) show the plots of the various transition temperatures against compositions. If the points representing T_i are joined (curve I), it is observed that the solubility of soap is very low, being only 5% at 165°. It increases rapidly as the temperature is increased. This curve shows three inflections (at 50%, 25% and 10%). This seems to indicate that the anisotropic material which separates out at temperatures below each portion of the curve between two consecutive points of inflection is not of the same type in all cases. This is realised in practice as shown below: (1) Up to the first inflection "neat soap" is formed from the isotropic liquid. (2) Below the portion of the curve after first inflection, the isotropic liquid does not give neat soap but "middle soap" which is immiscible with isotropic liquid and then neat soap. Again, what separates on solidification from this composition range is not waxy soap, but curds. (3) Below the portion after the second inflection (25%), the isotropic liquid gives a deposit of fine soap particles which give opaque gels. (4) Below the portion after the third inflection (10%), the systems which form transparent isotropic gels at higher temperatures become anisotropic. The curves II and III, obtained by plotting T_g and T_c respectively against temperature, show inflections which can be similarly interpreted.

Phases in the System.—An approximation of the phase boundaries can be made from the curves I, II and III, as shown in Fig. 1. (The vertical lines do not represent a sharp separation of two phases; they are marked only to show approximately the difference in phases on the two sides of the lines). The zones enclosing the various phases are:

- A. Homogeneous isotropic liquid or solution occupying a zone above the curve abcde, where d is the intersection point of curves I and II.
- B. A zone in which neat soap exists.
- C. A zone in which middle soap exists along with neat soap.
- D. A zone of soap particles which can form opaque loose gel.
- E. A zone of transparent, isotropic gels.
- F. A zone in which waxy soap exists.
- G. A zone of soap curds which get solvated on cooling.
- H. A zone of loose opaque gels which show tendency to form curd on standing.
- I. A zone of transparent gels which develop slight opacity but do not form curds, even after long standing at the room temperature.
- J. A zone in which soap curds develop on cooling and standing into more opaque white soap

As far as visual observations indicate, the compositions above 25% of the soap show the phenomenon of crystallisation. All these systems ultimately develop soap curds which are known to develop progressively more orderly structure on cooling from a high temperature.

FIG. 1

The colloidal phenomena are peculiar only to systems containing 25% or less of soap. In these systems, some of which contain particles looking like granules, syneresis is completely absent even after long standing, showing that both the loose and the firm gels are quite stable. Further, no curd formation takes place in the systems. On cooling, their consistency increases and ultimately opaque, white loose gels are formed. The process of the formation of gels, indicative of colloidal behaviour, is essentially dissimilar to crystallisation in which particles grow on cooling, leaving behind a mother-liquor. In the process of gelation, because of coalescence and adsorption, the primary particles grow in size and adsorb the liquid in which they are suspended.

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